

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 3, December- 2024 | Peer-Reviewed
Journal ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14359527

BETWEEN GAMIFICATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN EDUCATION

AUTHORS

Marcela Mezini Sales: Master's degree in Educational Sciences from the Universidad UNIDA - Paraguay. Graduated in Pedagogy from the Lapa Educational Faculty and Biological Sciences from the São Camilo University Center of Espírito Santo - Brazil. Postgraduate degree in Environmental Education and Arts, both from the São Francisco Faculty of Technology. Teacher of Science and Early Childhood Education.

Contact: marcelamezini@hotmail.com 28999673722

Mateus Eduardo Carneiro Alves: PhD student in Educational Sciences at the Universidad UNIDA - Paraguai. Master in Educational Sciences from the Universidad Columbia del Paraguai. Specialist in Braille, Special Education, Public Speaking, Geography, Environment and Sustainability, Management of Pedagogical Work. Graduated in Pedagogy and Geography. Teacher of Special Education.

Contact: mateuseduardoalves5@gmail.com 28999451951

ABSTRACT

The integration of gamification and artificial intelligence into education presents a field full of challenges and opportunities. Gamification, which uses game elements such as rewards, levels, and immediate feedback, has the potential to increase student engagement and motivation. By incorporating these elements, teachers can promote more active and collaborative learning, as well as develop critical thinking skills in students. However, it is crucial to balance the entertainment provided by games with educational objectives, ensuring that fun does not overshadow teaching and learning. It is also important to address issues of accessibility and inclusion, as not all students have access to advanced technologies, which can widen educational inequalities.